

Lowcost Method to Quantify Whitefly Oviposition

Analysis and Statistics

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Comparison of Instant Pot to Autocalve

Count Differences Before After Staining

```
## # A tibble: 2 x 4
##   clear_method median_diff_one mean_diff_one     N
##   <chr>          <dbl>         <dbl> <int>
## 1 autoclave      30           27.2     8
## 2 instantpot    15.5         18.2     8
```

Histogram of ins_auto_one_x

Histogram of ins_auto_one_y


```
##  
## Exact two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test  
##  
## data: ins_auto_one_x and ins_auto_one_y  
## D = 0.5, p-value = 0.2827  
## alternative hypothesis: two-sided  
  
## # A tibble: 2 x 3  
##   clear_method median_diff_two mean_diff_two  
##   <chr>          <dbl>          <dbl>  
## 1 autoclave      24             37.4  
## 2 instantpot    28             28.6
```

Histogram of ins_auto_two_x

ins_auto_two_x
Histogram of ins_auto_two_y


```
##  
## Exact two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test  
##  
## data: ins_auto_two_x and ins_auto_two_y  
## D = 0.375, p-value = 0.6224  
## alternative hypothesis: two-sided
```

Written Statements

The results of our Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests on the differences between stained and unstained egg counts found no evidence that the distribution is different using the Instant Pot method compared to the autoclave method for either counter one ($D = 0.5$, $p = 0.283$) or counter two ($D = 0.4$, $p = 0.622$).

Bubbles on the Leaf Surface

```
## # A tibble: 2 x 4
##   clear_method median_bubbles mean_bubbles    n
##   <chr>          <dbl>         <dbl> <int>
## 1 autoclave         2           2.5     8
## 2 instantpot       25          31.8     8
```

Histogram of ins_auto_bubbles_x

Histogram of ins_auto_bubbles_y


```
##  
## Exact two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test  
##  
## data: ins_auto_bubbles_x and ins_auto_bubbles_y  
## D = 1, p-value = 0.0001554  
## alternative hypothesis: two-sided
```

Written Statements

The mean number of bubble on the Instant Pot cleared leaf discs ($M = 31.8$, $Mdn = 25$, $N = 8$) was substantially higher than on the autoclave cleared leaf discs ($M = 2.5$, $Mdn = 2$, $N = 8$). Using a Kolmogorov-Smirnov test we found that the distribution of the number of bubbles for the Instant Pot method is significantly different from the distribution for the autoclave method ($D = 1$, $p < 0.001$). Taken together these results indicate that the formation of bubbles occurs more frequently when clearing using the autoclave when compared to the Instant Pot, however these experiments were only conducted on melon leaves and had low sample sizes.

Figure S2: Instant Pot Autoclave Differences

Figure S3 (images is okay)

Testing Surfactants to Reduce Bubbles on the Leaf Discs

Surfactant on Tomato Leaves

Count Differences Tomato

```
## # A tibble: 2 x 4  
##   surfactant median_diff_one mean_diff_one     n  
##   <chr>          <dbl>         <dbl> <int>  
## 1 no             2           0.286     7  
## 2 yes           3.5         4.25     8
```


Figure S2: Melon leaf disc response to clearing with the autoclave and the Instant Pot. A. Change in egg count after the staining process for each counting individual. B. Number of bubbles on stained leaf discs.

Histogram of tomato_surf_one_x

tomato_surf_one_x
Histogram of tomato_surf_one_y


```
##  
## Exact two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test  
##  
## data: tomato_surf_one_x and tomato_surf_one_y  
## D = 0.21429, p-value = 0.9329  
## alternative hypothesis: two-sided  
## # A tibble: 2 x 4
```

```
## surfactant median_diff_two mean_diff_two n
## <chr> <dbl> <dbl> <int>
## 1 no 13 10.4 7
## 2 yes 5 4.12 8
```

Histogram of tomato_surf_two_x

tomato_surf_two_x
Histogram of tomato_surf_two_y


```
##
## Exact two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test
##
```

```
## data: tomato_surf_two_x and tomato_surf_two_y
## D = 0.48214, p-value = 0.2522
## alternative hypothesis: two-sided
```

Written Statements The results of our Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests on the differences between stained and unstained egg counts for tomato leaf discs found no evidence that the distribution is different with surfactant or without surfactant for either counter one ($D = 0.2$, $p = 0.933$) or counter two ($D = 0.5$, $p = 0.252$).

Bubbles on Tomato Leaves

```
## # A tibble: 2 x 4
##   surfactant median_bubbles mean_bubbles    n
##   <chr>         <dbl>         <dbl> <int>
## 1 no             164.           177.     8
## 2 yes            71.5           88.6     8
```

Histogram of tomato_surf_bubbles_x

Histogram of tomato_surf_bubbles_y


```
##  
## Exact two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test  
##  
## data: tomato_surf_bubbles_x and tomato_surf_bubbles_y  
## D = 0.5, p-value = 0.2827  
## alternative hypothesis: two-sided
```

Written Statements The average number of bubbles on the tomato leaf discs with surfactant ($M = 89$, $Mdn = 72$, $N = 8$) was lower than on the tomato leaf discs without surfactant ($M = 177$, $Mdn = 165$, $N = 8$). Using a Kolmogorov-Smirnov test we found that the distribution of the number of bubbles on tomato leaf discs with surfactant is not significantly different from the distribution without surfactant ($D = 0.5$, $p = 0.283$).

Figure S4

Surfactant on Melon Leaves

Count Differences Melon

```
## # A tibble: 2 x 4  
##   surfactant median_diff_one mean_diff_one     n  
##   <chr>          <dbl>         <dbl> <int>  
## 1 no             26           30.7     7  
## 2 yes           18.5         22.1     8
```


Figure S4. Tomato leaf disc response to clearing with and without 0.1 % (v/v) Tween 20 surfactant in the LGW solution. A. Change in egg count after the staining process for each counting individual. B. Number of bubbles on stained leaf discs.

Histogram of melon_surf_one_x

melon_surf_one_x
Histogram of melon_surf_one_y


```
##  
## Exact two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test  
##  
## data: melon_surf_one_x and melon_surf_one_y  
## D = 0.5, p-value = 0.1751  
## alternative hypothesis: two-sided  
## # A tibble: 2 x 4
```

```
## surfactant median_diff_two mean_diff_two n
## <chr> <dbl> <dbl> <int>
## 1 no 41 45.3 7
## 2 yes 39.5 42.8 8
```

Histogram of melon_surf_two_x

Histogram of melon_surf_two_y


```
##
## Exact two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test
##
```

```
## data: melon_surf_two_x and melon_surf_two_y
## D = 0.25, p-value = 0.9005
## alternative hypothesis: two-sided
```

Written Statements The results of our Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests on the differences between stained and unstained egg counts for melon leaf discs found that the distribution are not significantly different with surfactant compared to without surfactant for either counter one ($D = 0.50, p = 0.175$) or counter two ($D = 0.25, p = 0.901$).

Bubbles on Melon Leaves at 0.1 % Span 80

```
## # A tibble: 2 x 4
##   surfactant median_bubbles mean_bubbles    n
##   <chr>          <dbl>         <dbl> <int>
## 1 no              10           10.7     7
## 2 yes              6            6.25    8
```

Histogram of melon_surf_bubbles_x

Histogram of melon_surf_bubbles_y


```
##  
## Exact two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test  
##  
## data: melon_surf_bubbles_x and melon_surf_bubbles_y  
## D = 0.32143, p-value = 0.6811  
## alternative hypothesis: two-sided
```

Written Statements The average number of bubbles on the melon leaf discs with surfactant ($M = 6.25$, $Mdn = 6$, $n = 8$) was lower than on the melon leaf discs without surfactant ($M = 10.7$, $Mdn = 10$, $n = 7$), but using a Kolmogorov-Smirnov test we found that the distribution of the number of bubbles on melon leaf discs with surfactant is not significantly different from the distribution without surfactant ($D = 0.32$, $p = 0.681$).

Bubbles on Melon Leaves at 0.5 % Span 80

```
## # A tibble: 2 x 4  
##   surfactant median_bubbles_05 mean_bubbles_05   n  
##   <chr>          <dbl>         <dbl> <int>  
## 1 no              3             6.14     7  
## 2 yes             1             2.62     8
```

Histogram of melon_surf05_bubbles_x

melon_surf05_bubbles_x
Histogram of melon_surf05_bubbles_y


```
##  
## Exact two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test  
##  
## data: melon_surf05_bubbles_x and melon_surf05_bubbles_y  
## D = 0.33929, p-value = 0.572  
## alternative hypothesis: two-sided
```

Written Statements The average number of bubbles on the melon leaf discs with surfactant ($M = 2.62$, $Mdn = 1$, $n = 8$) was lower than on the melon leaf discs without surfactant ($M = 6.14$, $Mdn = 3$, $n = 7$), but using a Kolmogorov-Smirnov test we found that the distribution of the number of bubbles on melon leaf discs with 0.5% Span 80 is not significantly different from the distribution without surfactant ($D = 0.34$, $p = 0.572$).

Figure S5

Figure S5. Melon leaf disc response to counting eggs in mineral oil with and without 0.1% (v/v) Span 80. A. Change in egg count after the staining process for each counting individual. B. Number of bubbles on stained leaf discs.

Surfactant on Sweet Potato and Cowpea Leaves

Count Differences Cowpea

```
## # A tibble: 2 x 4
##   surfactant median_diff_one mean_diff_one   n
##   <chr>          <dbl>         <dbl> <int>
## 1 no             21            19.3     7
## 2 yes           24.5          23.4     8
```

Histogram of cowpea_surf_one_x

cowpea_surf_one_x
Histogram of cowpea_surf_one_y


```
##  
## Exact two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test  
##  
## data: cowpea_surf_one_x and cowpea_surf_one_y  
## D = 0.28571, p-value = 0.8085  
## alternative hypothesis: two-sided  
## # A tibble: 2 x 4
```

```
## surfactant median_diff_two mean_diff_two n
## <chr> <dbl> <dbl> <int>
## 1 no 61 79.4 7
## 2 yes 56.5 57.4 8
```

Histogram of cowpea_surf_two_x

Histogram of cowpea_surf_two_y


```
##
## Exact two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test
##
```

```
## data: cowpea_surf_two_x and cowpea_surf_two_y
## D = 0.28571, p-value = 0.8466
## alternative hypothesis: two-sided
```

Written Statements

The results of our Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests on the differences between stained and unstained egg counts for cowpea leaf discs found no evidence that the distribution is different with surfactant or without surfactant for either counter one ($D = 0.29$, $p = 0.809$) or counter two ($D = 0.29$, $p = 0.847$).

Count Differences Sweet Potato

```
## # A tibble: 2 x 4
##   surfactant median_diff_one mean_diff_one     n
##   <chr>          <dbl>         <dbl> <int>
## 1 no              -11          -8.33     9
## 2 yes               4           4.88     8
```

Histogram of sweetpotato_surf_one_x

Histogram of sweetpotato_surf_one_y


```
##  
## Exact two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test  
##  
## data: sweetpotato_surf_one_x and sweetpotato_surf_one_y  
## D = 0.375, p-value = 0.4642  
## alternative hypothesis: two-sided  
  
## # A tibble: 2 x 4  
##   surfactant median_diff_two mean_diff_two    n  
##   <chr>          <dbl>         <dbl> <int>  
## 1 no              60           57.6     9  
## 2 yes             42           44.1     8
```

Histogram of sweetpotato_surf_two_x

sweetpotato_surf_two_x
Histogram of sweetpotato_surf_two_y


```
##  
## Exact two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test  
##  
## data: sweetpotato_surf_two_x and sweetpotato_surf_two_y  
## D = 0.44444, p-value = 0.2425  
## alternative hypothesis: two-sided
```

Written Statements The results of our Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests on the differences between stained and unstained egg counts for sweetpotato leaf discs found no evidence that the distribution is different with surfactant or without surfactant for either counter one ($D = 0.38$, $p = 0.464$) or counter two ($D = 0.44$, $p = 0.242$).

Figure S6

Figure S6. Change in egg count after the staining process for each counting individual when counted in mineral oil with and without 0.5% (v/v) Span 80. A. Cowpea. B. Sweet potato.

Comparison of Unstained and Stained Egg Counts

For these assessments of overall staining efficacy in each crop. Presence of surfactant was ignored in for this analysis.

Replace with wilxoc paired

Visualize data and test assumptions of egg count

Histogram of egg_count_one_stained

Histogram of egg_count_one_unstained

Histogram of egg_count_two_stained

Histogram of egg_count_two_unstained


```
##  
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test  
##  
## data: egg_count_one_stained  
## W = 0.95081, p-value = 0.0004781
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: egg_count_one_unstained
## W = 0.91593, p-value = 3.425e-06
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: egg_count_two_stained
## W = 0.8923, p-value = 2.199e-07
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: egg_count_two_unstained
## W = 0.86568, p-value = 1.484e-08
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: residuals(counter_one_egg_lmm)
## W = 0.99678, p-value = 0.9332
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: residuals(counter_two_egg_lmm)
## W = 0.90017, p-value = 6.108e-11
```

Data does not appear to come from a normal distribution (at least for counter 2), proceed with the non-parametric tests.

Overall Across Crops

```
### Overall Egg Count Change for Counter One (BVR)
```

Histogram of all_crops_for_perdiff_counter_one_differences


```
## # A tibble: 1 x 7
##   .y.      group1 group2   n1   n2 statistic      p
## * <chr>   <chr> <chr> <int> <int>   <dbl>   <dbl>
## 1 egg_count_one no     yes    110  110     942 0.00000000031

## # A tibble: 1 x 7
##   .y.      group1 group2 effsize   n1   n2 magnitude
## * <chr>   <chr> <chr>   <dbl> <int> <int> <ord>
## 1 egg_count_one no     yes     0.600  110  110 large

## [1] 62.5
```

Overall Egg Count Change for Counter Two (RL)

Histogram of all_crops_for_perdiff_counter_two_differences


```
## # A tibble: 1 x 7
##   .y.      group1 group2   n1    n2 statistic      p
## * <chr>   <chr> <chr> <int> <int> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 egg_count_two no     yes    110   110    178. 1.03e-17

## # A tibble: 1 x 7
##   .y.      group1 group2 effsize   n1    n2 magnitude
## * <chr>   <chr> <chr> <dbl> <int> <int> <ord>
## 1 egg_count_two no     yes    0.817  110   110 large
```

Written Statements: Overall Egg Count Change

First we looked at the data from all experiments across all crops and used a two-sided Wilcoxon signed-rank test to perform a paired comparison of egg counts before and after staining. Egg counts were significantly higher after staining for both the more experienced counter one ($Z = 942$, $p < 0.001$) and for the less experienced counter two ($Z = 178.5$, $p < 0.001$)

By Crop for Egg Count Change for Counter One (BVR)

```
## # A tibble: 5 x 10
##   .y.  group1 group2   n1    n2 statistic      p species p_value V_statistic
## <chr> <chr> <chr> <int> <int> <dbl> <dbl> <chr> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 egg_c~ no     yes    15    15    91  8.3 e-2 Cassava 8.3 e-2    91
## 2 egg_c~ no     yes    20    20   10.5 4.47e-4 Cowpea 4.47e-4   10.5
## 3 egg_c~ no     yes    28    28    0  3.98e-6 Melon 4 e-6      0
## 4 egg_c~ no     yes    17    17   91.5 4.92e-1 Sweet ~ 4.92e-1 91.5
## 5 egg_c~ no     yes    30    30   38.5 6.84e-5 Tomato 6.80e-5   38.5
```

Table S2

```
## Warning in stri_detect_regex(string, pattern, negate = negate, opts_regex =
## opts(pattern)): argument is not an atomic vector; coercing
```

```
## Warning in stri_detect_regex(string, pattern, negate = negate, opts_regex =
## opts(pattern)): argument is not an atomic vector; coercing
```

Table S2. Analyses of egg counts by the more experienced counter before and after staining for each crop.

Crop Species	N Samples	Unstained Median	Stained Median	Unstained Median Absolute Deviation	Stained Median Absolute Deviation	Percent of Samples Counts Increased	V Statistic	p-value
Cassava	15	32.0	33.0	7.41	8.90	33.33	91.0	0.083000
Cowpea	20	68.5	94.5	23.72	31.88	95.00	10.5	0.000447
Melon	28	22.0	43.5	11.12	22.98	100.00	0.0	0.000004
Sweet Potato	17	104.0	109.0	25.20	29.65	47.06	91.5	0.492000
Tomato	30	38.5	48.0	37.06	54.11	80.00	38.5	0.000068

Written Statements: Egg count by Crop for the More Experienced Counter One

The data was then separated out to evaluate the staining method performance in each crop individually. For the more experienced counter one, a significant increase in egg counts after staining was found in melons ($Z = 0.0$, $p < 0.001$), tomatoes ($Z = 38.5$, $p < 0.001$), and cowpeas ($Z = 10.5$, $p < 0.001$), but no significant difference was found in cassava ($Z = 91.0$, $p = 0.083$) or sweet potato ($Z = 91.5$, $p = 0.492$) (Table S2). Additionally, egg counts universally increased after staining in melons.

By Crop for Egg Count Change for Counter Two (RL)**Table S3**

```
## Warning in stri_detect_regex(string, pattern, negate = negate, opts_regex =
## opts(pattern)): argument is not an atomic vector; coercing
```

```
## Warning in stri_detect_regex(string, pattern, negate = negate, opts_regex =
## opts(pattern)): argument is not an atomic vector; coercing
```

Table S3. Analyses of egg counts by the less experienced counter before and after staining for each crop.

Crop Species	N Samples	Unstained Median	Stained Median	Unstained Median Absolute Deviation	Stained Median Absolute Deviation	Percent of Samples Counts Increased	V Statistic	p-value
Cassava	15	19.0	30	8.90	11.86	100.00	0.0	0.000721
Cowpea	20	27.5	71	18.53	29.65	100.00	0.0	0.000002
Melon	28	13.0	48	8.90	29.65	100.00	0.0	0.000004
Sweet Potato	17	57.0	95	10.38	34.10	82.35	19.5	0.007470
Tomato	30	23.5	52	20.02	49.67	90.00	18.5	0.000011

Written Statements: Egg Count by Crop for the Less Experienced Counter Two

For the less experienced counter two, a significant increase in egg counts after staining was found for cassava ($Z = 0.0$, $p < 0.001$), cowpea ($Z = 0.0$, $p < 0.001$), melon ($Z = 0.0$, $p < 0.001$), tomato ($Z = 18.5$, $p < 0.001$) and sweet

potato ($Z = 19.5, p = 0.007$) (Table S3). Additionally, egg counts universally increased after staining in cassava, cowpea, and melon.

Figure 2: Egg Count Change

Analysis of Percent Difference Between Counters

Percent difference is the absolute value of the difference between the egg counts from each counter divided by the average of the two egg counts.

The percent difference in egg counts between the more and less experienced counters is expected to decrease if staining makes egg counting easier (representing greater agreement between the two individuals).

Calculated as follows:

$$\text{count_perdiff} = \frac{\text{abs}(\text{egg_count_two} - \text{egg_count_one})}{((\text{egg_count_two} + \text{egg_count_one}) / 2)}$$

Where: egg_count_one = egg count value for the more experienced counter (BVR) egg_count_two = egg count value for the less experienced counter (RL)

Visualize Data and Check Assumptions


```
## [1] 110
```

```
## [1] 110
```


Figure 2. Egg count change before and after staining for each counter.

Histogram of unstained_allcrop_response

unstained_allcrop_response
Histogram of stained_allcrop_response


```
##  
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test  
##  
## data: unstained_allcrop_response  
## W = 0.97473, p-value = 0.03456  
##  
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test  
##
```

```
## data: stained_allcrop_response
## W = 0.76335, p-value = 5.012e-12
```

The histograms and the Shapiro-Wilk tests show the percent difference variable is highly right skewed. Therefore we will stick with non-parametric Wilcoxon paired rank sum tests.

Overall Percent Difference Across All Crops

```
## # A tibble: 1 x 7
##   .y.      group1 group2   n1   n2 statistic      p
## * <chr>   <chr> <chr> <int> <int>   <dbl>   <dbl>
## 1 count_perdiff no     yes    110  110    5731 1.39e-15

## # A tibble: 1 x 7
##   .y.      group1 group2 effsize   n1   n2 magnitude
## * <chr>   <chr> <chr>   <dbl> <int> <int> <ord>
## 1 count_perdiff no     yes    0.762  110  110 large
```

Written Statements: Overall Percent Difference Between Counters

Analysis of the percentage difference between counters across all crops found a significant decrease after staining ($Z = 5731, p < 0.001$).

By Crop Percent Difference

Table S4

```
## # A tibble: 5 x 9
##   `Crop Species` `(n) Samples` `Unstained Mean` `Stained Mean`
##   <chr>          <int>          <dbl>          <dbl>
## 1 Cassava        15            0.66           0.14
## 2 Cowpea         20            0.82           0.21
## 3 Melon          28            0.59           0.13
## 4 Sweet Potato   17            0.68           0.3
## 5 Tomato         30            0.59           0.21
## # i 5 more variables: `Unstained Median` <dbl>, `Stained Median` <dbl>,
## #   `Samples Where Percent Difference Decreased (%)` <dbl>,
## #   `Z Statistic` <dbl>, `p-value` <dbl>
```

Table S4. Analysis of percentage difference between egg counts for each crop.

Crop Species	(n) Samples	Unstained Mean	Stained Mean	Unstained Median	Stained Median	Samples Where Percent Difference Decreased (%)	Z Statistic	p-value
Cassava	15	0.66	0.14	0.72	0.10	86.67	114	0.000854
Cowpea	20	0.82	0.21	0.76	0.16	90.00	205	0.000019
Melon	28	0.59	0.13	0.56	0.10	85.71	384	0.000004
Sweet Potato	17	0.68	0.30	0.66	0.17	88.24	134	0.004640
Tomato	30	0.59	0.21	0.52	0.17	90.00	425	0.000016

Written Statements: By Crop Percent Difference Between Counters

Analyzing each crop individually, there was a significant decrease in percent differences after stain for all crops ($p < 0.001$, except sweet potato: $p = 0.005$) with over 85% of samples having lower percent differences after the staining process (Table S4).

Figure 3: Percent difference in egg counts

Costs and Time of the Staining Method

```
## `summarise()` has grouped output by 'counter'. You can override using the  
## `.groups` argument.  
## `summarise()` has grouped output by 'stained'. You can override using the  
## `.groups` argument.
```

Figure S8

Figure 3. Percent difference in egg counts across the two counting individuals.

Figure S8. Comparison of labor time requirements for counting eggs on unstained leaf discs, and performing the staining process then counting eggs on stained leaf discs.